

COHESIVENESS IN WORKING ON GROUP ASSIGNMENTS WITH SOCIAL LOAFING AMONG ISLAMIC COMMUNICATION AND BROADCASTING STUDENTS IN IAIN SALATIGA, INDONESIA

Nurul Istikomah¹

Qurratu Ayun²

Ahmad Fadil³

Moses Idongesit Peters⁴

^{1&2}Faculty of da'wah, Institut Agama Islam (IAIN) Salatiga

Jl. Lkr. Sel. Salatiga, Pulutan, Kec. Sidorejo, Kota Salatiga, Indonesia 50716

³Faculty of Education and Psychology, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta,

Jalan Colombo Yogyakarta No,1, Karang Malang, Yogyakarta, Indonesia 55281

Ahmadfadil.2022@student.uny.ac.id

⁴Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Akwa Ibom State University, Nigeria

mosesidongesit@aksu.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This correlation research was conducted to examine the the level of variation in cohesiveness group work, the level of social loafing in cohesiveness group work and the relationship between level of variation and level of social loafing in cohesiveness group work among Islamic Broadcasting Communication Students in Institut Agama Islam (IAIN) Salatiga, Indonesia. The researchers adopted Ringelmann's Social Loafing Theory of Robe-Pulling for a theoretical framework. The researchers also selected 91 students who met the required criteria out of 224 students who were purposively selected by the researchers from Islamic Communication and Broadcasting students of IAIN Salatiga who took Radio, TV, and Film Production Courses. Data collection in this study used a scale. Hypothesis testing was carried out using the Karl Pearson product-moment correlation technique. Findings of the study showed that the level of social loafing among students of the Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Study Programme in Indonesia was moderate and there was a significant relationship between cohesiveness in working on group assignments with social loafing of - 0.641 ($P < 0.05$), meaning that the higher the cohesiveness, the lower the social loafing and vice versa if the social loafing is high, the lower the cohesiveness. Researchers recommended that more group work among Islamic students will help pull students together and cohesive check will help reduce social loafing for more efficient group results.

KEYWORDS: Group Cohesiveness, Social Loafing, Islamic communication and broadcasting

INTRODUCTION

To create students who have high integrity, can adapt, are skilled, think critically, and can express ideas, a learning strategy or model is needed. One of the learning models educators use in higher education's teaching and learning process is the cooperative learning method. This method is a learning model that prioritizes groups and prioritizes cooperation in solving problems to apply knowledge and skills to achieve learning objectives. In working on group assignments, students need a sense of commitment, loyalty, and cohesiveness to their group.

The cooperative learning method is the basis of the strategy chosen by the lecturer in the learning process of the Radio, TV, and Film Broadcast Production course for students of the IAIN Salatiga Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Study Programme. The implication of the cooperative learning method applied in this course is the realization of the expectation that students can work together in solving problems and achieving group goals, as well as helping each other in understanding the material and completing group assignments, especially in making videos that are worked on collectively. Success in completing group assignments in Radio, TV, and Film Broadcast Production courses becomes an obligation and responsibility for each member of the group so that group goals can be achieved.

However, in reality, group work can provide more challenges than individual work. This is because group assignments must be done together to achieve the same goal. One of the challenges in working on group assignments is that it is still widely found that students reduce their performance to contribute and participate optimally because they think that there are still other people who will complete the task. In addition, individuals who carry out this behavior usually have the assumption that group tasks can be done by only a few members without the need for all members of the group to be involved. Apart from individual factors, group factors such as strangers among group members, ineffective communication between group members in coordinating the division of tasks, and the tendency of groups that have no motivation to unite and even no sense of mutual interest in-group members or studies, can be an obstacle to the success of group task work. Of course, group work is different from individual work, where students are more responsible and try as much as possible to get maximum results for themselves.

Problems related to reducing contributions in completing group assignments are often called social loafing behavior. Social loafing is a phenomenon in which group members experience decreased motivation and reduced effort, as well as their performance in working on group tasks. According to Baron and Byrne (2005), individuals who have social loafing behavior tend to make the necessary effort just to show good performance when compared to not working at all. This action can occur because social loafers have the assumption that there will be other members who will complete the task (Kotimah and Laksmiwati, 2021).

Previous research related to social loafing was first conducted by Ringelmann (Myers, 2012) on tug-of-war activities as his experimental test. Ringelman found that individuals who are in groups expend 50% less effort when compared to their total effort when working alone. While in another study conducted by Latane, William, and Harkins (Myers, 2012), who conducted experiments on clapping and shouting activities in groups, it was found that individuals reduced their efforts by 65% when clapping and 82% when shouting in groups

compared to when the individual did it alone. Social loafing occurs not only in physical activities but also in collective activities that require thinking or cognitive skills.

Social loafing can have negative impacts on both individuals and groups. Individually, students who do social loafing experience losses because they do not provide opportunities and limit themselves in developing their abilities or developing their own potential to gain knowledge, as well as new information on tasks that should be done. Individuals who do social loafing by reducing their contribution can also have a negative impact on the group, including the performance of group members becoming ineffective, decreasing group performance, decreasing productivity, and even affecting group cohesiveness.

One factor that causes social loafing behavior is group cohesiveness. Group cohesiveness has long been known to be a variable that affects social loafing. Group cohesiveness is an attraction that causes members to stay in the group. A cohesive group can reduce and even eliminate social loafing behavior for its members; this is because high group cohesiveness can be reflected in the tendency of group members to always be together and maintain togetherness in pursuing common goals to achieve effective needs (Carron in Zanu, 2017).

However, what happens in the field Research on group cohesiveness has been carried out a lot, some of which are research conducted by Fajrin et al. (2018) with the findings that the lower the cohesiveness, the higher the social loafing will be in organizational members. Another study was also conducted by Rahmi et al. (2021), which obtained the findings that cohesiveness and social loafing have a negative influence and relationship, where the higher the cohesiveness, the lower the appearance of social loafing.

The results of reinforcing data obtained from research conducted by Krisnasari and Purnomo (2017) show that there is a significant negative relationship between cohesiveness and social loafing in students, with a contribution of 41%, and the average student of the Faculty of Psychology is in the high cohesiveness category of 70.7% and the average in the low social loafing category is 76% of 167 students of the Faculty of Psychology of Satya Wacana Christian University who are research respondents. The results of this study are supported by the results of research data conducted by Rita et al. (2019), showing that of the total respondents of 250 students of SMAN 1 5 Indralaya, 171 (68.4%) students did social loafing in the low category and 79 students (31.6%) did social loafing in the medium category and 0% of students were classified as doing social loafing in the high category. The results of the data analysis show that student cohesiveness at SMAN 1 Indralaya is classified as high. Namely, 218 students (91.2%) and those who have cohesiveness classified as moderate 32 students (8.8%), and 0% of students who have cohesiveness in the low category. Based on the results of observations and unstructured interviews conducted by the author with fifteen students of IAIN Salatiga's Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Study Programme, it was found that the students admitted that they had contributed less when working on group assignments.

Another finding is that some students said they had found one of their task group members engaging in social loafing behavior, either disappearing by not contributing at all, copying other people's work, or only spending the necessary effort. This behavior is known to be motivated by ineffective communication between group members, unfair and unstructured task distribution, not knowing each other and not having closeness between group members

so that they feel unfamiliar, lack of motivation in the group to unite, and the assumption that there will be other people who can complete the task so that it encourages the perpetrator to make only the necessary effort, just to avoid feelings of guilt if compared to not contributing at all. Based on the observations and interviews described above, it is evident that social loafing does occur among students of IAIN Salatiga's Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Study Programme due to many factors, including group cohesiveness.

The results of previous studies also reinforce that group cohesiveness is one of the external factors related to and can affect social loafing. So, based on this, the author is interested in examining the problems that occur. Therefore, researchers will conduct research with the title of the relationship between Cohesiveness in Working on Group Assignments with Social Loafing in Students. The purpose of the study was to determine the level of variation in cohesiveness in group assignment work, provide an overview of the level of social loafing, and determine whether there is a relationship between cohesiveness in group assignment work and social loafing. The results of this study are expected to contribute to science, especially in the field of educational psychology, regarding social loafing and cohesiveness in group work.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Ringelmann Rope-Pulling Social Loafing Theory

Ringelmann (as cited in Kravitz and Martin, 1986) was interested in how agricultural workers could maximize their productivity. Ringelmann found that though groups outperform individuals, they usually do not perform to the extent they could if each individual worked at maximum capacity. For instance, in one study, he had people pull on a rope attached to a pressure gauge and found that the more people pulled, the further below their potential they would perform. If two individuals could pull 100 units separately, they would pull 186, not 200. Eight people working together could only pull 392, half of their sum potential of 800. Ringelmann (1913) attributed this phenomenon to two sources: coordination losses and motivation losses. He believed that coordination loss is as a result of lack of simultaneity of their efforts and was the main cause of social loafing, but also acknowledged that in some cases, workers lose motivation due to each man trusting his neighbour to furnish the desired effort.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative method to see the relationship between cohesiveness in group assignments and social loafing among Islamic Broadcasting Communication students of IAIN Salatiga in Indonesia. The population in this study was Islamic Communication and Broadcasting students who take Radio, TV, and Film Broadcast Production Course, which were 224 students. Sampling was done with a purposive sampling technique. The sample size for this study amounted to 91 students who met the criteria as a sample. Methods of data collection were psychological scales and observations.

The Cohesiveness Scale in Working on Group Assignments made by the researchers was compiled based on the dimensions of group cohesiveness from Rahmi et al., (2021). This scale consists of 41 favourable and unfavourable items. Meanwhile, the social loafing scale in working on group assignments was measured using the Social Loafing Scale, which was made

by the researchers based on the dimensions of social loafing from Chidambaram and Tung, 2005 consisting of 35 favourable and unfavourable items. The scale used in this study refers to the Likert model scale. The Likert model scale is a method of scaling individual statements that uses the distribution of responses as the basis for determining the scale value (Azwar, 2015). The Cronbach's Alpha value for the cohesive scale is 0.908, and the social loafing scale is 0.886, so both can be said to be reliable. The analysis technique used in this study was descriptive analysis to provide an explanation related to research subjects based on data from variables. Before conducting hypothesis testing, researchers conducted normality tests and linearity tests.

RESULTS

The sample in this study was 91 students from the Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Study Programme of IAIN Salatiga who met the criteria. If differentiated by gender, it is known that 60 female students (65.9%) and 31 male students (34.1%) became research respondents. Meanwhile, when viewed based on age, it is known based on data that as many as 15 students (16.5%) are 19 years old, 23 students (25.3%) are 20 years old, 29 students (31.9%) are 21 years old, 17 students (18.7%) are 22 years old, and 3 students (3.3%) are 23 years old, and 4 students (4.4%) are 24 years old. The description of the research data can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Description of Research Data

Variable	Data Hipotetik			
	Max	Min	Mean	SD
Cohesiveness in group work	31	124	77,5	15,5
Social Loafing	25	100	62,5	12,5

After conducting descriptive analysis, the author categorized the scores of respondents who had filled out the scale into low, medium, and high. The following is the categorization formulation:

Table 2. Categorization of Cohesiveness Score in Working on Group Assignments

Skor	Categorization	Frekuensi	Presentasi
$X < 62$	Low	1	1,1%
$62 \leq X < 93$	Medium	54	59,3%
$93 \geq X$	High	36	39,6%
Total		91	100%

Based on Table 2, categorization of cohesiveness scores in working on group assignments above, it can be seen that cohesiveness in working on group assignments in research respondents classified as low as 1 student (1.1%), which is classified as low as 54 students (59.3%), while those classified as high are 36 students (39.6%).

Table 3. Social Loafing Score Categorisation

Skor	Categorisation	Frekuensi	Presentasi
$X < 50$	Low	40	44%
$50 \leq X < 75$	Medium	51	56%
$75 \geq X$	High	0	0%
Jumlah		91	100%

Based on Table 3. categorization of social loafing scores above, it can be seen that social loafing in research respondents classified as low as 40 students (44%), which is classified as moderate 51 students (56%), while those classified as high are 0 students (0%).

Table 4. Hypothesis Test

		Kohesivitas	Social Loafing
Kohesivitas	Pearson Correlation	1	-.641**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	91	91
Social loafing	Pearson Correlation	-.641**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	91	91

Based on the output in Table 4. the results of the product-moment correlation hypothesis test above, it is known that the 2-tailed Sig value is 0.000, where this value is smaller than 0.05, which means that there is a significant relationship (correlation) between the cohesiveness variable in group work and the social loafing variable. In addition, based on the table output above, the person correlation value is -0.641, which means it shows the direction of the negative relationship (correlation).

DISCUSSION FO FINDINGS

Robbins and Judge (2015) state that cohesiveness is a condition in which group members have mutual interest in each other and are motivated to stay in the group. Cohesiveness in groups is influenced by several factors, including the existence of interpersonal attraction or attraction between individuals and one another (Forsyth, 2010). Lott and Lott (Forsyth, 2010) revealed that there are several factors that affect interpersonal attraction, including closeness, frequency of interaction, similarity, complementarity, reciprocity, and mutual respect; that way, they can change groups that do not have unity into cohesive groups. Cohesiveness in groups can also be influenced by other things, for example, the factor of members who often spend some time together with the group (Rita *et al.*, 2019).

Cohesiveness is a group unifying tool that can play a role in helping groups achieve the same goals. Groups that have high cohesiveness will try to become one. Strive to work together in achieving goals. Work together by bringing out all the abilities and potential of each of them to achieve group goals. In this way, members who are in groups that have high cohesiveness tend not to engage in social loafing behavior, or in other words; high

cohesiveness has a link to prevent social loafing behaviour. In addition, group cohesiveness can also affect group productivity.

Based on the data from the results of the scale (statements) filled out by the respondents, it is known that the average student already knows one member and another in the group; besides that, they also often spend time together outside of group assignment sessions, maintain communication with each other via chat or phone WhatsApp group, and help each other when there are problems in group assignments, so this can allow cohesiveness between students of Communication and Islamic Broadcasting IAIN Salatiga when working on group assignments can increase. The results of the descriptive data analysis in the table above can provide information and conclusions that the level of cohesiveness in working on group assignments owned by research respondents, on average, occupies a moderate category where there is 1 respondent with low cohesiveness, 54 respondents who have moderate cohesiveness, and 36 respondents with high cohesiveness.

Baron and Byrne (2005) stated that social loafing is a phenomenon that refers to a decrease in individual effort when in a group compared to when individuals work alone. In addition, Karau and Williams (Baron and Byrne, 2005) revealed that social loafing is defined as a reduction in motivation and effort that occurs when individuals work collectively in groups compared to when they work individually as independent colleagues. One of the factors that can affect social loafing is group cohesiveness (Anggaraeni and Alfian, 2015).

According to Michaelsen et al. (Goo, 2011), cohesiveness is significant in the achievement of group work. The existence of social loafing behavior can cause disappointment in students when working in groups. One of them is that it can cause sadness or envy among other group members because, with different performances, social loafing actors can produce the same value. This certainly has an impact on social relationships that can make group members experience loss of motivation, decreased group productivity, and reduced group cohesiveness. Based on the results of descriptive data analysis in the table above, it is concluded that the level of social loafing carried out by research respondents, on average, occupies a moderate category. Where as many as 40 students do social loafing in the low category, 51 students do social loafing in the medium category, and as many as 0 students or none do social loafing in the high category.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing data analysis in the output table 4.14 above, the 2-tailed Sig value is 0.000, where this value is smaller than 0.05, which means that there is a significant relationship (correlation) between the cohesiveness variable in group assignment work with the social loafing variable. In addition, based on the table output above, the person correlation value is -0.641, which means it shows the direction of the relationship (correlation) is negative and has a high degree of correlation. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, namely that there is a relationship between cohesiveness in working on group assignments and social loafing among Islamic Communication and Broadcasting students of IAIN Salatiga.

The acceptance of this hypothesis shows that group cohesiveness is a factor that plays a major role in the formation of social loafing (Sumantri and Pratiwi, 2020). Group cohesiveness is closely related to group member satisfaction; the more cohesive the group, the greater the level of group member satisfaction. This is because, in groups with high cohesiveness, members feel safe and protected, so communication becomes free, more open,

and trusting of each other. As explained by Hanurawan (2015), group cohesiveness is one of the factors that influence social loafing. In groups that have high group cohesiveness, group members can work together optimally to achieve group goals compared to group members who have low cohesiveness, where they tend to be unfamiliar and have no attachment to their fellow group members. This statement is in line with the research results obtained based on data analysis from psychological scales filled out by respondents, where individuals who act as group members and have high group cohesiveness tend to have high motivation in carrying out their duties and obligations in carrying out tasks in accordance with group policies.

This can be seen in group members who are enthusiastic about doing group assignments, enjoy discussing and conveying ideas, do not even slack off when given tasks, and try to maximize their potential for the group. In addition, individuals who have high group cohesiveness feel comfortable in the group so that they feel they need the group because groups that have high cohesiveness have a high sense of kinship; for example, fellow group mates always help each other if someone is having difficulty and group mates can be invited to discuss anything outside of the task. This is as explained by Prakoso (Arnida and Safitri, 2011) that cohesive group members are more often responsible, last longer in working to achieve difficult goals, are more motivated to complete group goals, and are more comfortable working in groups.

However, it is different with individuals who act as group members and have low group cohesiveness; they tend to feel lazy and lack enthusiasm for doing group tasks. This can be seen from the statements of individuals who still have the assumption that group tasks can be completed by other members, so they feel no need to work on group tasks to the fullest and can take advantage of the work of others. In addition, groups that have low cohesiveness can cause group members to lack attachment so that individuals feel strange and can even feel they don't need the group.

Based on the results of the above analysis, it can be concluded that high cohesiveness can reduce and even eliminate the occurrence of social loafing, and low cohesiveness can increase the occurrence of social loafing, or it can be said that there is a negative relationship between cohesiveness and social loafing, namely if group cohesiveness is high, social loafing is low and vice versa if social loafing that occurs is high, then group cohesiveness is low.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Krisnasari and Tjahjo Purnomo (2017), Panjaitan et al. (2019), and Pratama (2020), which state the findings that there is a negative relationship between social loafing and group cohesiveness, if social loafing is high then cohesiveness is low, and if social loafing is low then cohesiveness is high. In addition, the results of this study also support previous research conducted by Rahmi et al. (2021) and Kotimah Laksmiwati (2021), namely that cohesiveness is an influential factor that causes social loafing.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results that have been presented from the discussion that has been described regarding the Relationship between Cohesiveness in Working on Group Assignments with Social Loafing in Islamic Communication and Broadcasting Students of IAIN Salatiga, it was concluded that based on the descriptive data analysis of the level of cohesiveness in group work owned by students of Islamic Communication and Broadcasting

IAIN Salatiga, it is known that the average occupies a moderate category where there is 1 student (1.1%) with low cohesiveness, 54 students (59.3%) who have moderate cohesiveness, and 36 students (39.6) with high cohesiveness. Based on the results of descriptive data analysis of the level of social loafing in Islamic Communication and Broadcasting students, it is known that the average occupies a moderate category. Where as many as 40 students (44%) do social loafing in the low category, 51 students (56%) do social loafing in the medium category, and as many as 0 students (0%) or no one does social loafing in the high category. Based on the results of data analysis of hypothesis testing, the 2-tailed Sig value is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, which means that there is a significant relationship (correlation) between the cohesiveness variable in group assignment work and the social loafing variable. In addition, it is known that the person correlation value is -0.641, which means it shows the direction of the relationship (correlation) is negative and has a high degree of correlation. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, namely that there is a relationship between cohesiveness in working on group assignments and social loafing among Islamic Communication and Broadcasting students of IAIN Salatiga.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. More group work among Islamic students will help pull students together
2. Cohesive check will help reduce social loafing for more efficient group results
3. Students should be motivated to fully participate in group work
4. Students should be advised not to relinquish their responsibilities in group works

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